

The Effects of Rubber Keys' Structure and Its Packaging Tape on Automatic Assembly of Rubber Key in PCB Holes

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Abstract: *The structure and material characteristics of silicone rubber keys have a significant impact on how reliably the rubber keys' pins are assembled in the printed circuit board (PCB) holes. Pins that are too soft lead to insertion issues, whereas pins that are too rigid result in shock. The insertion is also impacted by interference between the insert pins and the PCB holes. Flexible placement machines that can quickly position components in a wide range of component types are becoming more and more necessary as surface mount technology (SMT) gains traction. When the author assembles the board, errors arise from improperly positioned PCB components in the layout. A number of dependability issues arise in this project as a result of improperly soldered components. The tape design for packing the rubber key was created by the author. The assembly procedure is impacted by the shape relationship between the tape and the key base.*

Keywords: SolidWorks software; SMT placement machine; Nozzle; Rubber keys; PCB

1. INTRODUCTION

A novel design for silicon rubber keys has improved conductivity and allowed for a quick and flexible automatic assembly procedure. Initially, the beginning data is written using the assumed dimensions of a sample key. After that, the final data was measured and converted into a two-dimensional graphic. The first product dimension was then measured. Assume the important information from the first data. Lastly, the final data was decided. The dimensions of the rubber keys could thus be easily ascertained. Ultimately, the rubber key's design was created based on the final measurements. Simulation of the assembly of rubber keys The chosen dimensions of the rubber key and nozzle design operate more quickly than earlier models, according to Solid Work 2D and 3D. By establishing a correlation between the measured pressure loss and the mass flow rate, differential pressure devices, like orifice plates and nozzles, are widely used in a variety of industries to estimate the mass flow rate passing through a conduit [1]. An entering nozzle is used to measure the fluid flow in a pipe. An aerodynamic open tunnel is used to examine the essence of movement. Frictional head loss is calculated by measuring the pressure drop in the pipe [2]. Nature has always been the clearest arranger of human existence. [3].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Initially, the sample keys' measurements were recorded. Measurements were made of the sample key's height, length, width, and separation between two keys. Figure 1(a) displays the sample key below in front view, Figure 1(b) displays the bottom view, and Figure 1(c) displays the top view..

Fig. 1. (a) Front view of the sample key.

Fig. 1. (b) Bottom view of the sample key.

Fig. 1. (c) Top view of the sample key.

2.1 Write the initial data

After measuring the sample key, the initial data chart was made and shown below.

Table 1. Initial data table

Specification	
Button length $L \pm 0.1$	16
Button width $B \pm 0.1$	7
Base height $H1 \pm 0.1$	1
High button $H \pm 0.1$	9.5
Key surface diameter $D \pm 0.1$	11
Conductor diameter $d \pm 0.1$	6.5
Page center distance $A \pm 0.1$	12
Pin diameter $\phi h \pm 0.1$	2
Pin cone end diameter $\phi h1 \pm 0.1$	1.2
Pin height $H \pm 0.1$	4
Heart $H1 \pm 0.1$	2.5
Pin deformation hole depth $\phi h2 \pm 0.1$	1.2
Pin deformation hole depth $h2 \pm 0.05$	3.5

2.2 Assume the key data from the initial data

After the final key data was assumed from the initial data. PCB hole’s diameter, the distance between two keys, height, and width was considered to assume the key data.

2.3 Final products dimension measurements

After considering all factors, the final data for the silicon rubber key was determined. The data table is below.

Table 2. Final data table

Specification	
Button length $L \pm 0.1$	16
Button width $B \pm 0.1$	10
Base height $H1 \pm 0.1$	1
High button $H \pm 0.1$	4
Key surface diameter $D \pm 0.1$	10
Conductor diameter $d \pm 0.1$	6
Page center distance $A \pm 0.1$	9
Pin diameter $\phi h \pm 0.1$	2
Pin cone end diameter $\phi h1 \pm 0.1$	0.85
Pin height $H \pm 0.1$	4
Heart $H1 \pm 0.1$	2.5
Pin deformation hole depth $\phi h2 \pm 0.1$	1.2
Pin deformation hole depth $h2 \pm 0.05$	3

2.4 Rubber keys assembly simulation (SolidWorks 2D)

The final dimension of the rubber key has been determined. According to the final dimension measurements, the SolidWorks 2D design of the rubber key was complete, as shown in fig. 2. The SolidWorks 2D design is below.

Fig. 2. SolidWorks 2D design based on final dimension.

2.4 SolidWorks 3D (Structure design, modeling, and assembly)

According to the final data fig. 3(a), fig3(b), fig 3(c), and fig 3(d) show the 3D design of the rubber key and PCB assembly.

Fig. 3. (a) PCB holes diameter measurement.

Fig. 3. (b) - SolidWorks 3D model of silicon rubber key and PCB (front view).

Fig. 3. (c) - Assembly of rubber key in PCB holes (Top view).

Fig. 3 (d) - Assembly of rubber key in Rubber key in PCB holes (Bottom view).

2.5 Design of rubber keys according to the final dimensions

Fig. 4. front view.

2.6 Nozzle design (prediction and determination of the nozzle data)

The rubber key dimensions are already determined. That’s why it must need to be considered the rubber key dimensions to predict the nozzle dimensions. Otherwise, it can’t pick and place the rubber key properly during the automatic assembly process. Here the nozzle design has shown in fig. 5. It is usually placed in a pipe in which fluid flows [4].

Fig. 5. B-B Section cut view and dimension determination design of the nozzle.

Here shown the B-B section cut. So that inside of the nozzle is clear to see. The dimension was taken as shown for designing the nozzle. The flexible dimension is determined that is perfect for our thesis and rubber key so that this nozzle can show better-suctioning performance during the automatic assembly process.

2.7 Assembly of the nozzle and the rubber key using SolidWorks 2D

Fig. 6. Assembly of the nozzle and the rubber key 2D.

Here the 2D assembly simulation of the nozzle and rubber key has shown in fig. 6. Here better effect is the main purpose and the result shows it has achieved the purpose, as the nozzle is suctioning the rubber key smoothly. The section view A-A helps to understand the design clearly. A nozzle plate, being a key part of steam engines, changes the flow directions of steam in a turbine used in a power plant [5].

2.8 Make SolidWorks 3D design simulation

simulation of the model using predicted parameters and validate the main parameters by simulation and experiments below in fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Assembly of the nozzle and the rubber key 2D.

3. RESULTS

Here the result is showing the design of the pick and place process by using SolidWorks. The process is very simple. The nozzle has better suction ability as it is a very

important part of this research work and for the automatic assembly process. The nozzle has the suction capability. At first, the nozzle head starts suctioning to hold the bottom part of the nozzle. The bottom part holds the key. After holding the bottom part the middle hole starts suctioning shown in fig. 10 (c). After that, the SMT machine takes the nozzle to the top of the rubber key. Here already fixed the cords of the key by a computer display. So it can pick the key from the tape [fig. 10 (d)] and place on the PCB [fig. 10 (e)]. Here good friction and deformation effects can be seen.

Fig. 8. (a, b, c, d, e) Pick and place Process simulation (Nozzle flow system).

Here is another nozzle 2D simulation [fig. 10 (f, g, h, i, j)] for our project. It has two extra pipes for better suction ability. These two pipes give extra force to suck the holes and push the buttons in the pick and place assembly.

Fig. 9. (f, g, h, i, j) Added two extra pipes in the pick and place Process simulation (Nozzle flow system).

3.1 Tape and packaging

The purpose of tape is to package rubber keys. Here, the rubber key is packed with tape. Here, a flexible tape is made to roll and allow the nozzle to pick up the key during the automated assembly process. The assembly process is impacted by the relationship between the tape cave shape and the rubber key base shape. The relationship between the rubber key and tape is that the rubber key requires the tape in order to be packed. To ensure that the rubber key slides easily into the tape cave, the design of the cave is based on the dimensions of the rubber key base. Here is a 2D SolidWorks drawing of the automatic rubber key assembling procedure. The section view of A-A and B-B is displayed in Fig. 10. as well as the design's measurements. The observed effect is excellent. This is the process of automatic assembling. Good effects are produced by the rubber key base form and the tape cave shape. For easier comprehension, the proportions used in the design are displayed here in fig. 11.

Fig. 10. SolidWorks 2D drawing of rubber key tape and packaging simulation.

Fig. 11. SolidWorks 3D drawing of rubber key tape and packaging simulation.

3.2 Analysis of the geometric relationship between the tape pit and key rectangular base

Here the dimensions of the tape and rubber key as shown in fig. 11.3 (a) and fig. 11.3 (b). The tolerance is (± 0.50).

Fig. 12. Rectangular tape dimension.

3.3 Deviation and tolerance

The rubber key is held in place using plastic tape. There will be numerous issues with the packing if the keys are not securely positioned in the tape. For instance, the key center and angle will not match the tape's center if the center and angle are not the same. Therefore, the tape pit dimension must be obtained after the key base dimension has been established. Additionally, the key is fitted into the tape using tolerance. The simulation's impacts and outcomes in SolidWorks are good. However, the tape and rubber key are not positioned properly. Because we are aware that the more low tolerance we employ, the more efficient our product will be.

Fig. 13. Shift of center due to the gap.

4. DISCUSSION

Aerodynamic science has greatly benefited from the study of the flow field over the bluff body [6]. The angle and center deviation that permit the pin to enter the PCB hole are obtained from the simulation. The distance is 0.5 mm. The gap causes both a change in the center and a departure in the angle. The angle and center deviation that permit the pin to enter the PCB hole must be known. We provide the maximum deviation in center and angle. A designed difference between an actual dimension and a nominal or theoretical size, or between an intermediate-stage dimension and an intended final dimension, is known as an engineering and machining allowance. The only definition of tolerance is the permissible difference between two limits of the same portion. Since it is difficult to manufacture a part in its exact dimension, tolerance is essentially necessary for manufacturing any part.

Here, we provide a tolerance of $+0.5/-0.5$ mm for the simulation.

The algebraic difference between the part's basic size and actual size is known as the deviation. Anything above the fundamental size is referred to as an upper deviation. Lower deviation, on the other hand, tends to be the gap

between the part's fundamental value and minimal limit. Deviation is the difference between the observed and actual values.

The total amount that a particular dimension can change is known as tolerance [7]. Here, the rubber key base and tape cave are designed using 16mm. Their tolerance is 16 ± 0.5 mm. This indicates that the range of this dimension value is 15.5 mm to 16.5 mm.

We can say that there is a discrepancy of 0.1 mm since the measured dimension from our simulation is 16.6 mm.

5. CONCLUSION

Silicone Dynamics may help with silicone keypad requirements by offering free engineering advice for the designs. Better, flexible, dependable, and fast automatic rubber key and nozzle assembly designs have been developed for this project in order to create better silicon rubber key structures. For easier and better conductivity, the switch uses a silicon keypad.

6. REFERENCES

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